

BeatNet: CRNN and Particle Filtering for Online Joint Beat Downbeat and Meter Tracking

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Main contribution:

- ✓ The 1st casual joint Beat, Downbeat and Meter tracking system
- ✓ SOTA online beat tracking performance
- ✓ Information gate technique
- ✓ Efficient cascade state space
- ✓ No meter prior knowledge requirement

System Overview

Input Signal

Pre-Processing

CRNN

Beat/Downbeat
Activations

Information Gate

Beat Tracking
Particle Filtering

Downbeat Tracking
Particle Filtering

NN Structure

Information Gate

Proposed cascade state space:

* F. Krebs, S. Böck, and G. Widmer, "An efficient state-space model for joint tempo and meter tracking," in *Proc. Int. Soc. Music Inf. Retr. Conf. (ISMIR)*, 2015, pp. 72–78.

Observation and transition models :

Beat observation and transition models

$$\phi_{b,k} = (\phi_{b,k-1} + \dot{\phi}_{b,k-1}) \bmod (\phi_b^{max} + 1),$$

$$p(\dot{\phi}_{b,k} | \dot{\phi}_{b,k-1}) = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\lambda_b \left| \frac{\dot{\phi}_{b,k}}{\dot{\phi}_{b,k-1}} \right| \right) & \text{if } \phi_{b,k} = 0 \\ \mathbb{1}(\dot{\phi}_{b,k} = \dot{\phi}_{b,k-1}) & \text{if } \phi_{b,k} > 0 \end{cases},$$

$$p(y_{b,k} | x_{b,k}) = \begin{cases} \max(b_k, d_k) & \text{if } \phi_{b,k} = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \max(b_k, d_k) \geq T \\ \gamma & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

Downbeat observation and transition models

$$\phi_{d,k} = (\phi_{d,k-1} + \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1}) \bmod (\phi_d^{max} + 1),$$

$$p(\dot{\phi}_{d,k} | \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1}) = \begin{cases} \lambda_d & \text{if } \phi_{d,k} = 0 \text{ and} \\ & \dot{\phi}_{d,k} \neq \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1} \\ 1 - \lambda_d & \text{if } \phi_{d,k} = 0 \text{ and ,} \\ & \dot{\phi}_{d,k} = \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1} \\ \mathbb{1}(\dot{\phi}_{d,k} = \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1}) & \text{if } \phi_{d,k} > 0 \end{cases}$$

$$p(y_{d,k} | x_{d,k}) = \begin{cases} d_k & \text{if } \phi_{d,k} = 0 \\ b_k & \text{if } \phi_{d,k} > 0 \end{cases},$$

Sequential Monte Carlo Particle Filtering:^{*}

$$p(x) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\omega^{(i)}}{\sum_{i=1}^N \omega^{(i)}} \delta(x - x^{(i)}),$$

$$p(x_{1:K}^{(i)} | y_{1:K}) \propto \prod_{k=1}^K p(y_k | x_k^{(i)}) p(x_k^{(i)} | x_{k-1}^{(i)}),$$

$$\omega_k^{(i)} = p(y_k | x_k^{(i)}) \omega_{k-1}^{(i)},$$

^{*} A. T. Cemgil and B Kappen “Monte Carlo methods for tempo tracking and rhythm quantization,” Journal of artificial intelligence research 18 (2003): 45-81.

Inference Model*:

* M. Heydari and Z. Duan, "Don't look back: An online beat tracking method using RNN and enhanced particle filtering," in In Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Acoust. Speech Signal Process. (ICASSP), 2021

Evaluation:

<i>Method</i>	<i>F-Measure Beats</i>	<i>F-Measure Downbeats</i>
Comparison of Online Methods		
<i>GTZAN Dataset</i>		
Aubio	57.09	—
BeatNet	<u>75.44</u>	<u>46.49</u>
Böck ACF	64.63	—
Böck FF	74.18	—
DLB	73.77	—
IBT	68.99	—
<i>Ballroom Dataset</i>		
Aubio	56.73	—
BeatNet	<u>77.41</u>	<u>47.45</u>
IBT	70.79	—
<i>Rock Corpus Dataset</i>		
Aubio	59.83	—
BeatNet	<u>73.13</u>	<u>44.98</u>
IBT	68.55	—
Comparison of Offline Methods		
<i>GTZAN Dataset</i>		
BeatNet + DBN	<u>80.64</u>	<u>54.07</u>
Böck	79.09	51.36

Appendix

Algorithm:

Algorithm 1 Joint Inference Procedure

beats, downbeats, meters = [], [], []

Sample $(x_{b,0}^{(i)}) \sim \mathcal{U}(S_b)$, $(x_{d,0}^{(j)}) \sim \mathcal{U}(S_d)$

Set $w_{b,0}^{(i)} = \frac{1}{N_b}$, $w_{d,0}^{(j)} = \frac{1}{N_d}$

for $k = 1$ to K **do**

Sample $(x_{b,k}^{(i)}) \sim p(\phi_{b,k}^{(i)} | \phi_{b,k-1}^{(i)})$, $p(\dot{\phi}_{b,k}^{(i)} | \dot{\phi}_{b,k-1}^{(i)})$

$\tilde{\omega}_{b,k}^{(i)} = \omega_{b,k-1}^{(i)} \times p(y_{b,k} | x_{b,k}^{(i)}) \quad \forall i \in N_b$

$\omega_{b,k}^{(i)} = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_{b,k}^{(i)}}{\sum \tilde{\omega}_{b,k}^{(i)}} \quad \forall i \in N_b$

if $\max(b_k, d_k) \geq T$ **then**

Resample $x_{b,k}^{(i)}$ according to $\omega_{b,k}^{(i)}$

end if

if $\text{median}(\phi_{b,k}^{(i)}) < T_w$ **and** $(k\Delta - \text{beats}[-1]) >$

0.4 $\text{median}(\dot{\phi}_{b,k}^{(i)})$ **then**

Append (beats, $k\Delta$)

Sample $(x_{d,k}^{(j)}) \sim p(\phi_{d,k}^{(j)} | \phi_{d,k-1}^{(j)})$, $p(\dot{\phi}_{d,k}^{(j)} | \dot{\phi}_{d,k-1}^{(j)})$

$\tilde{\omega}_{d,k}^{(j)} = \omega_{d,k-1}^{(j)} \times p(y_{d,k} | x_{d,k}^{(j)}) \quad \forall j \in N_d$

$\omega_{d,k}^{(j)} = \frac{\tilde{\omega}_{d,k}^{(j)}}{\sum \tilde{\omega}_{d,k}^{(j)}} \quad \forall j \in N_d$

Resample $x_{d,k}^{(j)}$ according to $\omega_{d,k}^{(j)}$

if $\text{mode}(\phi_{d,k}^{(j)}) == 0$ **then**

append (downbeats, $k\Delta$)

append (meters, $\text{mode}(\dot{\phi}_{d,k}^{(j)})$)

end if

end if

end for

Particle Filtering Formulas :

$$\begin{aligned} p(x) &= \frac{p'(x)}{c} = \frac{p'(x)}{c \pi(x)} \pi(x) = \frac{p'(x)}{c \pi(x)} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(x - x^{(i)}) \\ &= \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{\omega_i}{\sum_{i=1}^N \omega_i} \delta(x - x^{(i)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\pi(x_{0:K}^{(i)} | y_{0:K}) = \prod_{k=1}^K p(x_k^{(i)} | x_{k-1}^{(i)}) p(x_0^{(i)})$$

$$p(x_{0:K}^{(i)} | y_{0:K}) \propto \prod_{k=1}^K p(y_k | x_k^{(i)}) p(x_k^{(i)} | x_{k-1}^{(i)})$$

$$\omega_K^{(i)} = \frac{p'(x_{0:K}^{(i)} | y_{0:K})}{\pi(x_{0:K}^{(i)} | y_{0:K})} = \frac{p(y_K | x_K^{(i)}) p(x_K^{(i)} | x_{K-1}^{(i)})}{p(x_K^{(i)} | x_{K-1}^{(i)})} \omega_{K-1}^{(i)} \Rightarrow$$

$$\omega_K^{(i)} = p(y_K | x_K^{(i)}) \omega_{K-1}^{(i)}$$